

Human Psychology for Human Development

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Abstract:- In the sphere of social sciences, psychology is a vital subject. The development of social and humanitarian themes is rapidly rising in modern society. As a result, it is critical to engage the public in a discussion regarding the value of social sciences and related subjects. The fundamental goal of this research is to identify the human psychological factors that influence human development. Natural sciences and social sciences are the two primary categories in the sciences. Natural science is the study of the natural or physical environment and the conduct of experiments based on it. They conduct their research by maintaining control of the situation within the Science Laboratory based on the facts. Social sciences, on the other hand, conduct experiments in society but do not control human behavior. They allow people to act as they wish across society, and they simply study the situation and draw conclusions based on human behavior. Sociology and psychology are combined in human psychology. According to certain social psychologists, anthropology and social psychology are also intertwined. Human psychology studies the growth and pattern of human thought and behavior, which is largely impacted by human or social development. Social interaction,

interrelationships, social influences, attitudes, perspectives, and pro-social behaviors all have a direct impact on social development.

Keywords:- Social Psychology, Social Development, Social Factors, Social Sciences, Society

I. INTRODUCTION

The term "psychology" comes from the Greek word "psyche," which means "breath," "soul," and "spirit," and the word "logos," which means "discourse" or "study of." It was the 1980's, and the subject was largely discussed in the modern period of philosophy. Following World War II, people began to investigate the mind and behavior. They stated that psychology is not only the study of the human mind, but also the study of human conduct. JB Watson was the first to propose the theory of human behavior.

After a few decades, Sigmund Freud introduced psychoanalysis, which was a theory that explained the human mind and mental processes. Conscious, subconscious, and unconscious processes are used to process all human activities.

Psychology is a study that encompasses both social and natural sciences. Psychology refers to scientific strategies for subject growth. Psychology, on the other hand, discussed both physical and mental aspects of human behavior. As a result, the fields of physiological psychology and neurological psychology have developed, and researchers are looking at how biological effects affect human social behaviors such as family relationships, social interaction, and social perception. There are a few significant psychosocial approaches that have influenced social psychology's development. Biological perspectives, cognitive perspectives, behavioral perspectives, evolutionary perspectives and humanistic perspectives are only a few examples. According to the American Psychological

Association (APA), psychology has approximately sixty sub-fields.

All of these sub-fields lay the way for the advancement of human action, as well as the advancement of society. Social psychology is a study of human behavior from a broad perspective. According to Allport (1985), social psychology is the scientific study of how the actual, imagined, or suggested presence of others influences people's ideas, feelings, and behaviors. Social psychology was founded in the United States at the turn of the twentieth century. Norman Triplett's experiment on the phenomena of social facilitation in 1898 was the first published study in this field.¹ The study of human social relations,

communities, and societies is known as social psychology. Individuals and (members of) social groupings' cognition, motivation, and behavior are all influenced by personal, situational, and societal influences.² Social Psychology also investigates how social impact, social perception, and social interaction affect individual and group behavior.

II. SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTEXT FOR SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT

Some major issues in social psychology can be interpreted as important variables in social development. Social development can be implemented once human development is completed. The following are some social psychological facts to consider.

- Social Persuasion
- Perceptions of Others
- Cognition in social situations
- Relationships with others
- notion of oneself
- Attractiveness to others
- Attitudes towards others
- (Social/Group) Behaviour

¹Triplet, N. (1898). The dynamogenic factors in peacemaking and competition. *American Journal of Psychology*. 9, 507-533.

²Hewstone M. Three lessons from social psychology: multiple levels of analysis, methodological pluralism, and statistical sophistication. In: McGarty C, Haslam A, editors. *The Message of Social Psychology*. Oxford: Blackwell; 1997. pp. 166–181

- Aggression in Social Situations
- Discrimination and prejudices
- Culture

III. SOCIAL PERSUASION

Social impact includes peer pressure, conformity, and obedience. The ability of organizations in society to influence change for the betterment of the society or country is critical for social progress. Social influence is defined as a man or woman's inner thoughts, feelings, attitudes, or behaviors as a result of interactions with other men or women or a group. Conformity, strength, and authority are not the same as social influence. Conformity occurs when a person presents a specific opinion or action in order to fit into a specific situation or to meet the expectations of a specific person. Social influence, on the other hand, is the process through which people's thoughts and behaviors change as a result of interacting with others who are regarded to be similar, desirable, or knowledgeable... Whether or whether a change in reported viewpoint or attitude (conformity) indicated an actual private shift, it was deemed a case of social influence.³

IV. PERCEPTIONS OF OTHERS

The study of how people develop impressions of and draw conclusions about other people is known as social perception. We learn about other people's sentiments and emotions by observing their physical appearance, as well as their verbal and nonverbal interactions. People communicate without words in a variety of ways, including facial expressions, tone of voice, hand gestures, and body position. The cognitive mechanism that assists us in forming impressions of individuals around us is known as social perception. Our taught, possibly even subconscious attitudes toward other individuals based on any number of their distinguishing qualities aid us in comprehending a situation and determining appropriate behavior. The mental process of taking up signs and indications from others that help us establish an early impression of who they are is known as social perception. To develop a picture of what to expect from any new social contact, our brains may rely on stereotypes or previous similar encounters.

³ [https://www.verywell.com/retrieved from 1/9/16](https://www.verywell.com/retrieved%20from%201/9/16)

It now piques the curiosity of a wide range of professionals, including social scientists, psychologists, philosophers, and anthropologists, because it incorporates elements of cognitive processing, individual and interpersonal conduct, group perceptions, and group behavior. Perhaps no more succinctly than the title of one anthology of writings on the issue, *Person Memory*. "The work of making sense of ourselves and our behavior necessitates that we understand there can be as much value in the blink of an eye as there can be in months of rational thought," Malcolm Gladwell concluded after researching the utility of social perception. We can also use social perception against ourselves by absorbing other people's impressions of us. The *Looking Glass Self* is a notion that analyzes how our sense of self is impacted by how we feel others perceive us.⁴

Social perceptions are created as a result of a combination of experience and expectations about how a person's defining physical or other overriding traits will influence how we anticipate that person to be. Ethnicity, nationality, religion, class, and disabled people are all mentioned as instances.

V. COGNITION IN SOCIAL SITUATIONS

The way people interpret, analyze, recall, and use knowledge about their social context is referred to as social cognition. The processing, storage, and application of social information are all part of social cognition. Social cognition is a theoretical and empirical method to understanding social psychological topics by looking at the cognitive basis of whatever social phenomenon is being investigated. This is to say, its focus is on an examination of how information is processed, stored, represented in memory, and finally used in perceiving and interacting with the social world. Instead than being a content area within social psychology, social cognition is a strategy for reading any subject matter area within social psychology. As a result, a social cognition viewpoint can be used to investigate a wide range of topics,

including individual perception, attitudes and mindset interchange, stereotyping and prejudice, decision-making, the self-idea, social verbal interaction and influence, and intergroup discrimination.

VI. RELATIONSHIPS WITH OTHERS

Human behavior, attitudes, feelings, and beliefs are heavily influenced by social relationships. Social psychologists investigate at attachment, connection, love, attraction, and other aspects of interpersonal interactions to see how they affect people. The value of interpersonal relationships is studied in social psychology, as well as how close ties effect individuals.

⁴[https://www.questia.com/library/psychology/cognitive-psychology/perception/social-perception/retrieved 1/9/16](https://www.questia.com/library/psychology/cognitive-psychology/perception/social-perception/retrieved%201/9/16)

VII. NOTION OF ONESELF

Self can be defined as the process by which humans grow to know and comprehend themselves. According to the notion of self, it is a study of how self-perception relates to social relationships, as well as how one's inner life affects one's interactions with others and the social world. As a result, it raises concerns regarding self-awareness, self-esteem, and self-expression, among other things. Self-concept is divided into two elements, according to the social identity theory: personal identity and social identity. Personal identity encompasses personality traits and other characteristics that distinguish each individual. Our social identity encompasses the groups to which we belong, such as our community, religion, college, and other organizations.

According to Bracken (1992), there are six distinct domains related to self-concept:⁵

- The ability to engage with people is referred to as social.
- Competence is defined as the capacity to meet basic demands.
- Affect is the awareness of one's own emotional states.
- Feelings about one's attractiveness, health, physical condition, and general appearance
- Academic performance - whether you succeed or fail in school
- Family - how successfully a person functions as part of a family unit.

Carl Rogers, a humanist psychologist, believed that self-concept was divided into three parts: How you see yourself, or your self-image. It's critical to remember that one's self-image does not always correspond to reality. People may have an exaggerated sense of self-worth and believe they are better than they are. People, on the other hand, are more likely to have negative self-images and to detect or exaggerate defects or inadequacies. Self-esteem refers to how well you regard yourself. Self-esteem is influenced by a variety of factors, including how we compare ourselves to others and how others react to us. We are more likely to acquire high self-esteem when people respond positively to our actions. When we compare ourselves to others and see where we fall short, it can be detrimental to our self-esteem. Your ideal self is the person

you want you could be. In many circumstances, how we view ourselves and how we would like to see ourselves are incompatible.⁶

⁵Bracken, B. A. *Examiner's Manual for the Multidimensional Self-esteem Scale*. Austin, TX

⁶Weiten, W., Dunn, D. S., & Hammer, E. Y. *Psychology Applied to Modern Life: Adjustments in the 21st Century*. Belmont, CA

VIII. ATTRACTIVENESS TO OTHERS

One of the most important factors in social development is social attraction, which is based on the attitudes of social beings. The evolution of society requires a national and worldwide degree of attractiveness. Most cultures strive to become more appealing by promoting social empowerment, welfare, and progress.

IX. ATTITUDES TOWARDS OTHERS

Attitudes are critical determinants of our perceptions of, and movements toward, all aspects of our social environment. Attitudes are made up of a complicated web of evaluative values, emotions, and proclivity towards specific behaviors. Attitudes are a person's interpretation of herself or others. Our lives are influenced by our attitudes, and human behavior is influenced by our attitudes. It has an impact on people's perceptions and thoughts about society. When it comes to maintaining interpersonal relationships, attitudes control other people's actions and attitudes. Attitudes can also influence collective behavior in a community.

X. (SOCIAL/GROUP) BEHAVIOUR

Most people are aware that groups behave differently than individuals, according to a social psychological approach. Social and group behaviors are more advantageous and beneficial. It can be positive, but it can also be detrimental. For example, if a political party decides to change some policies within the party, a few members may disagree, resulting in conflict inside the group. On the other hand, when it comes to making decisions for the country's progress, they may agree as a group in Parliament. Social behavior, also known as prosocial behavior, entails assisting and working with the other party or group.

XI. AGGRESSION IN SOCIAL SITUATIONS

Humans are prone to aggressiveness in society. Aggression, as a social psychological trait, can cause people to harm themselves or others in society. Human rights violations, gender-based violence, crimes, and social crimes are only a few examples.

XII. DISCRIMINATION AND PREJUDICES

Prejudices and discrimination can grow at any level of society. It is founded on human social structure and attitudes. Discriminations have an impact on human behavior. People in Sri Lanka, for example, have discriminated based on ethnicity or caste throughout the last few decades.

XIII. CULTURE

Social psychologists distinguish between two basic cultural groupings. Individualistic cultures stress individual interests over group interests, whereas collectivistic cultures prioritize group interests over individual interests. There are a few common features that can be used to define individualistic cultures, such as Individual rights are cherished to a middling degree, independence is highly regarded, and being reliant on others is generally regarded as disgraceful or embarrassing. People tend to be self-sufficient. People are considered "accurate" in individualistic societies if they are strong, self-reliant, forceful, and impartial. In contrast, in collectivist cultures, traits such as self-sacrifice, dependability, beneficence, and utility to others are valued more highly. Whereas collectivism emphasizes the importance of organization, social cooperation, independence, and self-sufficiency, collectivist cultures are more likely to seek help from their circle of relatives and friends during difficult times, whereas individuals living in more individualist cultures are more likely to face problems on their own.

XIV. SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT THROUGH SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGY

Development is a multi-dimensional system involving the restructuring and reorientation of the entire economic and social system, not only an economic phenomena. "Development is a process of improving the quality of all human lives with three equally significant features," Todaro (1985)⁷ writes. Raising people's living standards, such as incomes and consumption, levels of food, medical services, and education, through relevant growth processes; Creating conditions conducive to the growth of people's self-esteem through the establishment of social, political, and economic systems and institutions that promote human dignity and respect; and Increasing people's freedom to choose by expanding the range of their choice variables, such as varieties of goods and services in telecommunications. As a result, according to social psychology, all human actions, whether direct or indirect, have an impact on social evolution. Individuals and groups were affected by political, economic, social, and cultural development, as well as social influence, social perception, social cognition, interpersonal relationships, social attraction, social attitudes, social behavior (social/group), social aggression, prejudices, and discrimination.

⁷Todaro M.P. (1985), Economic Development in the Third World, Longman, UK

XV. CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this paper is that the advancement of social psychology leads to societal advancement. Human intra-relationships and inter-relationships are shaped mostly by social development. Human attitudes and behaviors have the power to influence society not just in theory, but in practice. Individual behavior in a social setting under prosocial behavior is the goal of social psychology as a social science. Social psychology can be defined as a branch of psychology that studies the nature and causes of human behavior in social circumstances. As a result, it examines human conduct as it is influenced by the use of others, as well as the social context in which this occurs. As a result, social psychologists study the factors that cause us to behave in a certain way in the presence of others, as well as the circumstances that lead to positive behavior/movements and moods. Social psychology is concerned with how emotions, thoughts, beliefs, intentions, and dreams are formed, as well as how such psychological elements influence interpersonal relationships. The development was mostly centered on the physical aspects of civilization. On the other hand, Mantel, or human spiritual development, exists in society. Social psychological elements have an impact on social development as a result of human mind growth.

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